

THE EPIC OF ERGENEKON OR THE RETURN OF THE TURKIC PEOPLES

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ANNOTATION

The article provides opinions and feedback from scientists and researchers about the Ergenikon qahramanic epic about the return of the Turkic peoples, presented in Jahan's largest encyclopedia.

Keywords: Turkish, Uzbek, Kazakh, Karakalpak, bashkir, Turkmen, Tatar, Kyrgyz, Göktürk, wiki, Wikipedia

INTRODUCTION

Ergenekon Legend or Ergenekon Epic; according to sources, the story about the rebirth of the Göktürks.

14-century Mosque of people penned Hamedani-tevârih of his work is very tacü "Mujallad-i Awwal" (First Book: The History of the Mongol) in the "Bab-I Awwal" (Chapter One: the history of the Turkish and Mongol tribes) that is described in the epic of the creation of the Mongols in the legend, 17th - century Sibani, grandson of the Khan of Khiva and the Khanate of Abu'l Ghazi penned his mighty Genealogy-the Turkic epic of creation as told forensic work of the Mongols is also, according to some sources, the Turkish is a saga. According to the two mentioned historical sources, when the brothers named Nekuz (Nüküz) and Qiyani (Qiyani) and their wives were defeated by the Tatars, he first went to a narrow and steep place called Ergene Kon (Persian: قون ارگنه; Ergene Qon), and when his family multiplied and could not fit there in 400 years, he left Ergenekon. It is thought that when they left Ergenekon, they were in the Börteçine of their guide. According to other sources, the Göktürk nation living in the Ergenekon region was pressured by the country that owns that region. It was impossible to get out of the region where Ergenekon residents were located. Because they are surrounded by mountains. The Ergenekonians lit a big fire to get out of here, melted these mountains and survived.

However, there are also researchers who claim that it is an epic belonging to the Turks, citing similarities with the creation epic of the Göktürks. According to Talat Sait Halman also, the Wolf is an extended version of the saga; a mythological creature, freed from the danger of extinction thanks to the

protection of Bozkurt, Bozkurt thanks again from the valley surrounded by mountains and impassable of a community that told the story of the Turkish Ergenekon claims. According to other opinions, there are legends that are Deciphered in a similar way between the Turks and the Mongols. The legend has also sometimes been associated with Nowruz.

It was the legendary homeland of the Turks in Central Asia. According to the description of the Russian historian Gumilev, it carries the meaning of a steep slope.

Although various arguments have been put forward about where Ergenekon really is, there is no definite finding on this subject. According to the descriptions in the ancient works, it is mentioned that Ergenekon is located in the Altay mountains, in the Baluch Mountain

The legend, which was oral at first, was later mentioned in various sources and put into writing. It is also called as "Ergenekon Legend" because there is no consensus about all of it and it is in the form of a short summary in written texts.

The story known as the Ergenekon Saga consists of two main parts:

- * ensuring the continuity of the lineage with the help and protection of a steppe wolf;
- * settling in a valley surrounded by impassable mountains and then getting out of here.

The first story was told as the origin story of the Turks in three separate Chinese chronicles. The summary of the second story has been included in Chinese sources again. Reşidüddin Hamedani's *Mosque'üt-Tevarih* and the second one is Abul Gazi Bahadır Khan's works titled *Genealogy-i Türki*, such as XIII-XVII. in various works written between Dec., the valley in the legend is called "Ergenekon"; however, in these sources, the heroes of the legend are not Turks, but Mongols.

Decin DeWeese, professor of Central Asian history, points out that the motif of liberation from captivity in a cave or valley is told in different ways by the peoples of Central Asia and notes that it is common for similar stories to be told between Turks and Mongols.

At a later date, under the auspices of bozkurd, the theme of descent and the motives of settling in the valley and escaping from the valley were combined, and it began to be referred to as a Turkish epic under the title "Ergenekon Epic". According to Fuat Köprülü, the Mongols mentioned in the legend are actually the Oghuz because of the family of Turkish origin that existed in the lineage of

Genghis Khan. This is the reason for the similarity in the stories of Rashid al-Din Hamadani and Abul Ghazi Bahadur Khan.

AD VI. the second half of the century and the VII. in Chinese chronicles written between the turn of the century, it is told that as a result of a war, a child, the only surviving member of his tribe, was raised by a wolf and survived death and continued his lineage Decently. According to Chinese sources, the Göktürks are descended from this lineage. This story was later told within the framework of the Ergenekon saga. Again, VI. in Chinese sources belonging to the XVIII century, the story of their liberation from a cave where the Turks were held captive or from a valley surrounded by mountains is transmitted. However, the name "Ergenekon" is not included in these narratives.

The story "Exit from Ergenekon", XIII. it was described in the Mosque'üt-Tevarih of Reşidüddin Hamedani, one of the Ilkhanid palace officials, at the end of the century (volume I, part I). However, the hero of the story described in this text is not the Göktürks, but the Mongols. In this text, the story of the exit from the Ergenekon valley carries weight, the motif of the "child born of a wolf" does not take place.

In the following periods, XV. and XVI. Persian Turkish and Chagatai written in the centuries of the Ergenekon epic in the works written as a Mongolian legend is included. XV.-XVI. genealogy of the Turks (Genealogy of the Turks), a work written in Persian in the XVI centuries. Tevarih-i Güzide-i Nusretname, XVI, written in Turkish at the beginning of the century. Zubdatul-Athar, written in Turkish in the middle of the XI century, and XVI. the legend of Ergenekon is conveyed in texts such as the Abdullah Name, a Persian book from the end of the century. According to Isa Ozkan, professor of Turkish Language and Literature, XVII. the same story was told in Abul Gazi Bahadır Khan's work Genealogy-i Türki in the XVII century. It is seen that the Mongols are the subject of this work, which was written using Camiü't-Tevarih.

According to the encyclopedia Meydan Larousse, XIX. the Russian orientalist Nikita Biçurin (Iakin F / Hyacinth), who lived in the first half of the century, tells a similar story of the exit from the valley surrounded by steep mountains as the story of the descent of the ancestors of the Turks, without giving the name "Ergenekon" and bases this narrative on Chinese sources.

During the reign of Il Khan, a descendant of Oguz Khan in the Mongol province, the ruler of the Tatars, Joy Khan, waged war on the Mongol country. He defeated the army under Il Khan with the help of the Kyrgyz and other tribes. They killed everyone in Il Han's country. Only Il Han's young son Kyan, his wife Nüküz and

his nephew managed to escape and escape. They decided to go to a place where the enemy would not find them.

Following a path along which wild sheep were walking, they came to a narrow gorge in a high mountain. Passing through this gorge, when they came to a place where there were streams, springs, various plants, meadows, fruit trees, various hunting, they thanked God and decided to stay here. They called this place "Ergene Kon" in the sense of "mining place". The sons of Kiyān and Nuqūz multiplied. Four centuries later, they and their herds multiplied so much that they could not fit into Ergenekon. The place of the passage where their ancestors came here had been forgotten. They searched for passages in the mountains around Ergenekon. A blacksmith said that if the iron part of the mountain is melted, it can be opened. They lined up a row of wood and a row of coals where the iron had been and lit the fire.

They fanned it all at once with seventy bellows that they put in seventy places. The iron melted, enough room was made for a loaded camel to pass. The Turks, the descendants of Il Khan, returned to their old homeland with renewed strength, they avenged their ancestors. They celebrated a holiday every year on March 21, the day they left Ergenekon. During this feast, they angered a piece of iron, and when the iron turned crimson, first the Hakan, then the gentlemen, put the iron on the anvil and beat it. It is still celebrated today as both a freedom and spring holiday.

October Turkish Genealogy was translated from Chagatai to Ottoman Turkish by Ahmet Vefik Pasha, this translation was serialized in the newspaper Tasvir-i Efkār from October 1863. The section on the Ergenekon legend was published in the 143rd issue of the newspaper dated November 8, 1863. published in the issue.

During the Balkan War, the legend of Ergenekon was attracted by nationalist writers. Ziya Gökalp's poem dealing with the theme of Ergenekon was published in the issue of Türk Duygu magazine dated May 8, 1913 with the title "Turkish Ananesi: Ergenekon"; the same poem was included in Ziya Gökalp's 1914 book of Red Birth with the title "Ergenekon". Ömer Seyfettin also published a poem on the theme of Ergenekon in the April 9, 1914 issue of Halk Doğru magazine. This poem by Ömer Seyfettin largely bears traces from Ziya Gökalp's Ergenekon.

Rıza Nur covered the theme of Ergenekon in his epic work Oğuzname, published in Alexandria in 1928.

It is claimed that the Ergenekon epic was written by Yakup Kadri Karaosmanoğlu as a Turkish legend during the Turkish War of Independence

and that it is a story that has not been found in the Ottoman Empire, the smallest trace of which was found in the Seljuks. However, Orhan Hammer responded to these statements; that the works written by Yakup Kadri described the War of Independence, not Ergenekon, and that the Hive Khan Abu'l Gazi Bahadır Khan was the 17th. he denied by saying that he mentioned the Ergenekon Epic in his work "Genealogy Turki", which he wrote in the century.

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